

1 **The projected changes in the surface energy budget of the CMIP5 and Euro-**
2 **CORDEX models: are we heading toward wetter growing seasons in Central**
3 **Europe?**

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ABSTRACT

15 We analyze the surface energy budget from four climate model ensembles and its future
16 changes in the 21st century under the RCP8.5 or SSP5-8.5 scenario. High-resolution Euro-
17 CORDEX regional climate models (RCMs) and their driving CMIP5 global climate models
18 (CMIP5-D) are first tested in Central Europe against observational datasets. Evaluation reveals
19 the added value of RCMs in terms of spatial variability and smaller biases. CMIP5-D are
20 affected by the positive bias of global irradiance that propagates into other radiation and heat
21 fluxes. There are strong differences in the projected surface energy budget components between
22 RCMs and CMIP5-D. There is an increase in global irradiance for most of the year in CMIP5-D
23 and other GCM ensembles that is translated into a year-round enhancement of the absorbed solar
24 energy and balanced by higher latent heat flux, except in summer, when the sensible heat flux
25 rises strongly. Together with strong warming and reduced precipitation in summer, this leads to
26 warm, sunny, and dry conditions with reduced evapotranspiration and higher drought stress for
27 vegetation. In the RCMs, the reduction in global irradiance dominates, and it is translated into a
28 round-year reduction in the net balance of longwave radiation and stronger latent heat flux. The
29 first months of the growing season show weaker warming associated with higher
30 evapotranspiration and precipitation. In summer, precipitation drops, and global irradiance and
31 warming rise, but they fall behind the changes in the GCMs. Compared to GCMs there are less
32 visible signs of conditions leading to a reduction in evapotranspiration or a shortage of soil water
33 in the RCMs in summer.

34 **1. Introduction**

35 The future evolution of the climate and its impact on life on Earth is currently one of the
36 biggest questions and challenges. The current knowledge about climate and its future
37 development is regularly reviewed by assessment reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on
38 Climate Change (IPCC). The most recent 6th Assessment Report of IPCC Working Group 1
39 (IPCC 2021) is also accompanied by the new Interactive Atlas of Climate Change (Gutiérrez et
40 al. 2021), which provides deeper insight into expected climate change at the regional level. The
41 climate projections summarized in the 6th IPCC report are based on simulations of a large
42 ensemble of global climate models (GCMs) from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
43 phase 6 (CMIP6) (Eyring et al. 2016; O'Neill et al. 2016) and their comparison with a previous

44 generation of climate models from the CMIP5 ensemble (Taylor et al. 2012). The Interactive
45 Atlas of Climate Change also includes projections that are based on simulations of regional
46 climate models (RCMs) from the global CORDEX initiative (Giorgi et al. 2009). The CORDEX
47 projections presented in the IPCC Atlas were created by dynamical downscaling (Wilby and
48 Wigley 1997) of the CMIP5 GCMs using the state-of-the-art RCMs.

49 A significant advantage of RCM projections compared to those based on GCMs is their
50 better spatial resolution, which may reach up to 12 km in some regions (e.g., Europe). In
51 contrast, the spatial resolution of the vast majority of CMIP6 GCMs remains at the level of 100-
52 300 km. Many important mesoscale processes in the climate system, which shape the climate at
53 the regional level, are thus not fully resolved in GCMs but may be well captured in RCMs.
54 Therefore, there is a continuing effort in the scientific community to bring RCM simulations
55 toward finer spatial scales of kilometers with full resolution of atmospheric convection (Prein et
56 al. 2015; Kendon et al. 2021; Lucas- Picher et al. 2021). Additionally, there is an effort to
57 increase the complexity of RCMs and include further components of the climate system, similar
58 to CMIP Earth System Models (Giorgi 2019). As noted by Giorgi (2019), RCM projections are
59 the preferred choice for the analysis of climate change and its impacts on the subcontinental
60 scale corresponding to, e.g., individual countries or even smaller administrative regions. RCMs
61 thus represent the beginning of the information and processing chain that ends with proposals of
62 targeted adaptation measures, political decisions, and the related financial costs.

63 Central Europe is a transition area between two important poles of observed and projected
64 climate change in Europe: warmer and wetter Scandinavia and warmer but drier Mediterranean
65 (Coppola et al. 2020; Gutiérrez et al. 2021). The uncertainty in the projected changes in the
66 Central European climate will further increase if different model ensembles (GCM vs. RCM) are
67 considered (Bartók et al. 2017; Fernández et al. 2019; Boé et al. 2020; Coppola et al. 2020).
68 However, significant differences between GCMs and RCMs also appear when both model
69 ensembles are compared with observed trends or long-term mean values of climate variables in
70 the second half of the 20th century (Enriquez-Alonso et al. 2017; Bartók et al. 2017).

71 Enriquez-Alonso et al. (2017) found that RCMs are unable to capture the observed decadal
72 trend in total cloudiness in the Mediterranean area, while their driving GCMs can reproduce it
73 and show a statistically significant decreasing trend corresponding to observations. Similarly,

74 Bartók et al. (2017) described significant differences in the projection of global radiation over
75 Europe in the 21st century among Euro-CORDEX RCMs and their driving GCMs. They also
76 detected different trends of global radiation in both model ensembles when compared with
77 observations and attributed these differences to time-invariant aerosol concentrations in RCMs.
78 The latter can also partly affect air temperature trends over Europe simulated by RCMs driven by
79 reanalysis. As noted by Nabat et al. (2014), the air temperature trends in this type of RCM
80 simulation do not correspond to observations.

81 The most prominent difference between RCM and GCM projections in Europe is a reduction
82 in summer warming by RCMs (Sorland et al. 2018). It is also associated with the smaller
83 decrease in precipitation and smaller increase in global radiation in RCMs compared to GCMs
84 (Boé et al. 2020). However, the projected seasonal means or various climate indices based on air
85 temperature or precipitation may also differ among Euro-Cordex RCMs, their driving CMIP5
86 GCMs or newer CMIP6 GCMs in other seasons (Fernandéz et al. 2019; Coppola et al. 2020),
87 although less significantly than in the summer.

88 Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain disagreements among GCM and RCM
89 projections of air temperature, precipitation, or global radiation in Europe during the 21st century.
90 The absence of time-varying anthropogenic aerosols in most RCM simulations plays a major role
91 in the differences in solar radiation changes (Boé et al. 2020; Taranu et al. 2022). Boé et al.
92 (2020) also noted that RCMs simulate a much larger increase in evaporation over the
93 Mediterranean Sea. This could likely affect the relative humidity changes over the continent,
94 leading to a smaller reduction in cloud cover, precipitation and finally evapotranspiration and
95 thus a smaller increase in air temperature. Nevertheless, the causes of these evaporation changes
96 over the sea remain unclear. Schwingshackl et al. (2019) proposed that RCM projections may
97 also underestimate future warming due to missing plant physiological CO₂ responses. This
98 process is captured by most GCMs, but plants do not reduce their transpiration under elevated
99 CO₂ conditions in RCMs, which leads to lower surface temperatures, especially during
100 temperature extremes. However, plant physiology seems to be unlikely to act as the dominant
101 factor in the detected GCM/RCM discrepancies according to Taranu et al. (2022). Fernandéz et
102 al. (2019) noted that the overall design of the Euro-Cordex ensemble with only a few favored
103 GCMs selected for downscaling, and a larger share of some RCMs in the final ensemble may

104 affect the final climate change signal of the RCM ensemble. Similarly, Taranu et al. (2022) have
105 shown that inconsistencies in the projected climate change may be limited when GCMs and
106 RCMs share similar settings (same resolution, same physics, same forcings).

107 The main goal of this study is to analyze differences in projections of individual components
108 of the surface energy budget (Earth's surface radiation and heat balance) provided by Euro-
109 CORDEX RCMs and their driving CMIP5 GCMs across the Central European domain. Special
110 emphasis is placed on the projected changes in latent and sensible heat fluxes. Both turbulent
111 heat fluxes may act as indicators of bioclimatic conditions, and their changes reflect the
112 combined effect of air temperature, precipitation or global radiation on vegetation and
113 ecosystems. While the changes in the sensible heat flux affect the temperatures, including the
114 extremes, the boundary layer depth and consequently the cloud formation (Katul et al. 2012), the
115 latent heat flux is closely connected to water vapor transport, which represents a major part of
116 the hydrological cycle across Central Europe. Another aim of the study is to evaluate
117 components of the surface energy budget simulated by Euro-CORDEX RCMs and their driving
118 CMIP5 GCMs in the past climate. Unlike temperature or precipitation, the surface energy budget
119 components are less often a subject of validation. This is to identify potential shortcomings of
120 climate models that could affect the interpretation of future projections.

121 **2. Data and methods**

122 We analyze the components of the Earth's surface energy budget available from climate
123 models with the focus on the summer half-year (April to September). The selected period
124 roughly corresponds to the growing season in the study area (Central Europe). Individual
125 radiation and heat fluxes are considered as long-term monthly averages over a period of 25 years
126 (1981-2005 in the past and 2076-2100 in the future).

127 The selected study area (further referred as Central Europe) is defined as the rectangle
128 between 9–21° of the eastern longitude and 47–54° of northern latitude. The area is
129 approximately centered over the Czech Republic but covers a larger area including parts of
130 Germany, Poland, Slovakia, Hungary, Austria and Switzerland. It also includes part of the
131 eastern ridge of the Alps (see Fig. 1). The region is characterized by a complex landscape with
132 various vegetation types (mainly agricultural land, pastures, and mixed forests) and altitudes
133 mostly up to 1000 m. It is an intensively used agricultural landscape and a source of water for

134 several major European rivers. The territory of all above-mentioned countries including their
 135 parts outside of the defined study area is considered as a wider area of Central Europe.

136

137 Fig. 1. Study area in Europe with highlighted locations of FLUXNET sites used for
 138 evaluation of the climate models and ERA5-Land reanalysis. More detailed information about
 139 the FLUXNET sites can be found in Table A1 in Appendix.

140 *a. Climate variables*

141 The simplified Earth’s surface energy budget can be written as follows:

142
$$S_d - S_u = L_u - L_d + H + LE + G \quad (1)$$

143 where S_d is the incoming shortwave solar radiation (also called global irradiance), S_u is the
 144 solar radiation reflected from the Earth’s surface, L_u is the outgoing longwave radiation from the
 145 Earth's surface, L_d is the incoming longwave radiation from the atmosphere, H is the sensible
 146 heat flux, LE is the latent heat flux (positive when energy is transported from the surface to the
 147 atmosphere) and G is the heat flux into soil. Note that according to the sign convention used,
 148 positive values of S_d and L_d represent a gain of energy on the Earth’s surface, while positive
 149 values of S_u , L_u , H and LE correspond to a loss of energy on the Earth’s surface. The vertical
 150 heat flux from/to soil is not used in the study, as it is not commonly available in climate model

151 data. The terms on the left side of Equation (1), S_d and S_u , represent the net balance of shortwave
152 radiation, NetSW:

$$153 \quad NetSW = S_d - S_u \quad (2).$$

154 Similarly, the first two terms on the right side of Equation (1), L_u and L_d , represent the net
155 balance of longwave radiation, NetLW:

$$156 \quad NetLW = L_u - L_d \quad (3).$$

157 The difference of both balances, NetSW and NetLW, forms the net radiation balance of the
158 Earth's surface, NetRAD:

$$159 \quad NetRAD = NetSW - NetLW \quad (4).$$

160 To study the relative contributions of the turbulent energy fluxes (H and LE) to the Earth's
161 surface energy budget, we use the evaporative fraction (EF), defined as follows:

$$162 \quad EF = \frac{LE}{H + LE} \quad (5).$$

163 *b. Climate models*

164 We consider four sets of climate models: one set of RCMs, two sets of CMIP5 GCMs and
165 one set of CMIP6 GCMs. The RCM data came from the European part of the CORDEX global
166 experiment (Euro-CORDEX) and have a spatial resolution of 0.44° on the RCM native rotated
167 grid (corresponding to ca. 50 km grid spacing). Unlike previous studies (Stagehuis et al. 2013;
168 Knist et al. 2017), we exclusively work with simulations driven by CMIP5 GCMs and not with
169 reanalysis, as our goal is to analyze the climate change signal and understand how GCM-RCM
170 modeling pairs (as a tool to simulate the future) are successful in capturing the climate of the
171 recent past. We also do not use the more detailed Euro-CORDEX simulations with a 0.11°
172 resolution, as the potential added value of RCMs compared to GCMs should already be apparent
173 in the coarser resolution of 0.44° . Our selection should also suppress possible errors in RCM
174 simulations that stem from a gap in the horizontal resolution between RCM and its driving GCM
175 data or from limitations of RCM physical parameterizations under very high resolution.

176 In total, we considered 9 RCM simulations (Table 1), where all the necessary surface energy
177 budget data were available at the Earth System Grid Federation data nodes at the time when this

178 study was initiated. There are 4 different RCMs in the selected Euro-CORDEX ensemble;
 179 however, their share is not equal. While two RCMs (CLM4.8.17 and HIRHAM5) are represented
 180 by only one simulation each, the RCA4 simulation driven by various GCMs has the largest share
 181 (5 out of 9 simulations).

RCM name	Driving GCM				
	CNRM-CM5	EC-EARTH	HADGEM2-ES	IPSL-CM5A-MR	MPI-ESM-LR
CLM4.8.17					X
HIRHAM5		X			
RACMO22E		X	X		
RCA4	X	X	X	X	X

182 Table 1. Summary of Euro-CORDEX RCMs and their driving CMIP5 GCMs.

183 The second model ensemble used in this study is composed of 5 GCMs that serve as a source
 184 of lateral boundary conditions for Euro-CORDEX RCMs. All driving GCMs (hereinafter
 185 CMIP5-D) are mentioned in Table 1 and listed with more details in Table 2.

186 Climate projections of RCMs and CMIP5-D are also compared to projections of larger model
 187 ensembles. Firstly, it is a 15-member ensemble (further referred to as CMIP5 ensemble)
 188 composed of 5 CMIP5-D and 10 additional GCMs from Phase 5 of CMIP. Secondly, it is a
 189 group of 17 GCMs from Phase 6 of CMIP. All models from both larger ensembles are listed in
 190 Table 2. There are two reasons to include additional GCMs into the analysis:

- 191 1) to understand how CMIP5-D projections, based on 5 GCMs only, are consistent with the
 192 mean climate change signal of the larger ensemble of CMIP5 models,
- 193 2) to see how RCM and CMIP5-D projections representing the previous generation of
 194 climate models are related to the climate change signal derived from the latest generation
 195 of CMIP6 GCMs.

Ensemble designation		Number	GCM name	Ensemble member	Horizontal resolution, long. x lat. [°]
CMIP5	CMIP5-D	1	CNRM-CM5	r1i1p1	1.41 x 1.41
		2	EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	1.13 x 1.12
		3	HadGEM2-ES	r1i1p1	1.88 x 1.25
		4	IPSL-CM5A-MR	r1i1p1	2.50 x 1.27
		5	MPI-ESM-LR	r1i1p1	1.88 x 1.87
	-	6	BCC-CSM1-1	r1i1p1	2.81 x 2.79

		7	CESM1-BGC	rlilp1	1.25 x 0.94
		8	CESM1-CAM5	rlilp1	1.25 x 0.94
		9	CMCC-CESM	rlilp1	3.75 x 3.71
		10	CMCC-CMS	rlilp1	1.88 x 1.86
		11	GFDL-CM3	rlilp1	2.50 x 2.00
		12	GFDL-ESM2G	rlilp1	2.50 x 1.52
		13	INM-CM4	rlilp1	2.00 x 1.50
		14	MRI-ESM1	rlilp1	1.13 x 1.11
		15	NorESM1-M	rlilp1	2.50 x 1.90
	CMIP6	1	AWI-CM-1-1-MR	rlilp1f1	0.94 x 0.94
		2	BCC-CSM2-MR	rlilp1f1	1.13 x 1.12
		3	CESM2	r4ilp1f1	1.25 x 0.94
		4	CMCC-CM2-SR5	rlilp1f1	1.25 x 0.94
		5	CMCC-ESM2	rlilp1f1	1.25 x 0.94
		6	CNRM-CM6-1-HR	rlilp1f2	0.50 x 0.50
		7	GFDL-CM4	rlilp1f1	1.25 x 1.00
		8	GFDL-ESM4	rlilp1f1	1.25 x 1.00
		9	EC-EARTH3	rlilp1f1	0.70 x 0.70
		10	EC-EARTH3-CC	rlilp1f1	0.70 x 0.70
		11	EC-EARTH3-VEG	rlilp1f1	0.70 x 0.70
		12	HadGEM3-GC31-MM	rlilp1f3	0.83 x 0.56
		13	INM-CM5-0	rlilp1f1	2.00 x 1.50
		14	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	rlilp1f1	0.94 x 0.94
		15	MRI-ESM2-0	rlilp1f1	1.13 x 1.12
		16	NorESM2-MM	rlilp1f1	1.25 x 0.94
		17	TaiESM1	rlilp1f1	1.25 x 0.94

196 Table 2. Summary of CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs.

197 For all sets of climate models, we calculated an ensemble mean as a simple arithmetic
198 average across all ensemble members. Due to the absence of outgoing shortwave and longwave
199 radiation (S_u and L_u) data in the EC-EARTH model, the CMIP5-D ensemble mean for all
200 radiation balances (NetSW, NetLW and NetRAD) was based on only 4 GCMs. When plotting
201 the GCM ensemble mean on a map, the data of individual GCMs were first interpolated to the
202 common grid of 1.5° resolution in longitude and latitude, and then the ensemble mean map was
203 calculated. Interpolation can be skipped when plotting maps for RCMs, as all models share the
204 same grid in rotated geographic coordinates.

205 The projected changes in the surface energy balance were analyzed for the last quarter of the
206 21st century (2076-2100) and compared with the historical period 1981-2005. We used climate
207 model simulations following the representative concentration pathway RCP8.5 scenario in case

208 of RCMs and CMIP5 GCMs and the Shared Socioeconomics Pathway (SSP) scenario SSP5-8.5
209 for CMIP6 GCMs. The selected scenarios expect a continuing increase in greenhouse gas
210 concentrations toward the end of the 21st century. The results of climate model simulations based
211 on the RCP8.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios are thus expected to deliver the most significant changes
212 in climate parameters compared to the current conditions.

213 To evaluate the significance of the results, we consider the projected ensemble mean changes
214 significant only if they exceed the standard deviation calculated from changes of individual
215 ensemble members.

216 *c. Observational data*

217 To evaluate the performance of climate models in the recent past (1981-2005), we used the
218 European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ERA5-Land reanalysis
219 (Muñoz-Sabater et al. 2021) as the main validation dataset representing the observational data.
220 ERA5-Land was created by interpolation of the main reanalysis ERA5 (Hersbach et al. 2017)
221 into a finer spatial grid with a resolution of 0.1° in latitude and longitude. The validation was
222 focused on a comparison of long-term monthly means of individual surface energy fluxes
223 spatially averaged over the whole study area and their temporal course over the period from
224 April to September.

225 To validate the global irradiance, we used two additional observational datasets: the E-OBS
226 dataset of gridded station observation version 22e (Cornes et al. 2018) and the SARA-2 dataset
227 (Pfeifroth et al. 2019) created within the Climate Satellite Application Facility of EUMETSAT.

228 The E-OBS dataset is based on the interpolated daily global irradiance data (directly
229 measured or calculated from sunshine duration measurements) stored in the European ECA&D
230 database and originally coming from station networks of national weather services and other data
231 providers. Similar to ERA5-Land, E-OBS data are available in a regular grid with a mesh size of
232 0.1° in latitude and longitude.

233 SARA-2 global irradiance data were derived from satellite observations and offer a higher
234 spatial resolution of 0.05° in latitude and longitude. However, the first data were available as late
235 as 1983, i.e., two years later than that in the ERA5-Land, E-OBS or climate models.

236 Finally, we used measurements of surface energy balance components from selected stations
237 of the FLUXNET network in Central Europe. The data from FLUXNET sites cover the period
238 2001–2018; however, availability may differ among stations (Table A1 in Appendix A).
239 FLUXNET records were used here to illustrate surface turbulent heat fluxes behavior in different
240 biomes typical for Central Europe and to compare with climate model data.

241 *d. Evaluation procedure*

242 Mean bias and spatial correlation over the study area were used as two metrics to evaluate the
243 performance of climate models by comparison with ERA5-Land reanalysis in the period 1981–
244 2005. All data was transferred to the common regular grid of 1.5° resolution in longitude and
245 latitude and then both metrics were calculated. RCMs were first interpolated to the regular grid
246 of 0.5° resolution in longitude and latitude and then upscaled by spatial averaging in the matrix
247 of 9 grid points. As ERA5-Land comes on the regular 0.1° grid it was upscaled by spatial
248 averaging in the matrix of 225 grid points. GCMs were transferred from their native grids to the
249 1.5° grid by interpolation only.

250 **3. Results**

251 *a. Evaluation in past climate conditions*

252 The aim of this section is to analyze the performance of RCMs and their driving GCMs by
253 comparison with ERA5-Land reanalysis in the period 1981–2005.

254 1) RADIATION FLUXES

255 The annual course of global irradiance, NetSW and NetLW over the study area shows very
256 good agreement among RCMs and ERA5-Land reanalysis (Fig. 2a-c). In summer, global
257 irradiance and NetSW is slightly higher in RCMs (up to +9 W/m² or ca. +5%), but when other
258 validation datasets (E-OBS and SARA-2) are considered, there is good agreement among these
259 datasets and RCMs, better than in the case of ERA5-Land. NetLW in RCMs is underestimated
260 during the entire growing season (Fig 2c), the most significantly in spring (down to -7 W/m² or
261 ca. -10%). Spatial correlations of global irradiance and NetSW (Table 3) are higher than 0.8,
262 sometimes even over 0.9, with only one exception (NetSW in May). On the other hand, NetLW
263 correlations are lower in RCMs, ranging from 0.54 in May to 0.91 in September. When the RCM
264 data is checked visually on its native grid, there is a clear signal of global irradiance reduction in

265 the mountains, e.g. over the Carpathians or Eastern Alps, in summer that is related to the annual
266 course of convection and cloudiness in the region (Fig. A1 in Appendix A). The summer
267 reduction in global irradiance is also clearly visible in the SARAH-2 satellite data but not evident
268 in the E-OBS and ERA5-Land data.

269

271 Fig. 2. Seasonal course of selected components of the surface energy budget [W/m^2] over
 272 Central Europe from April (IV) to September (IX) as simulated by Euro-CORDEX RCMs, their
 273 driving GCMs (CMIP5-D), and ERA5-Land (ERA5L): global irradiance (a), net shortwave
 274 radiation (b), net longwave radiation (c), the sum of latent and sensible heat flux (d), latent heat
 275 flux (e) and sensible heat flux (f). For global irradiance other two validation datasets, E-OBS and
 276 CM SAF SARA-2, are also displayed.

277 In the case of CMIP5-D, spatial correlations of radiation fluxes are very low (under 0.5),
 278 especially in summer months (Table 3). From April to July spatial correlations of NetLW are
 279 even higher than for global irradiance or NetSW, an attribute that is not present in RCMs.
 280 However, the main feature of CMIP5-D is the positive bias of all radiation fluxes from May to
 281 September (Fig. 2a-c or Table 3). In June and July global irradiance and NetSW are
 282 overestimated by approximately 35 W/m^2 and NetLW on 13 W/m^2 or ca +20% in relative
 283 comparison.

Parameter	Model ensemble	mean bias [W/m^2]						spatial correlation [-]					
		IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
S_d	CMIP5-D	0	12	38	34	19	17	0.52	0.27	-0.09	0.36	0.65	0.85
	RCM	2	-2	9	6	2	8	0.93	0.81	0.87	0.80	0.93	0.95
NetSW	CMIP5-D	3	15	37	31	17	13	0.45	0.48	-0.09	0.32	0.60	0.82
	RCM	-2	-1	9	5	0	4	0.87	0.65	0.83	0.80	0.93	0.95
NetLW	CMIP5-D	2	7	13	13	9	9	0.58	0.67	0.24	0.38	0.54	0.43
	RCM	-5	-7	-4	-3	-4	-2	0.78	0.54	0.74	0.71	0.69	0.91
H + LE	CMIP5-D	3	11	23	18	8	4	0.51	-0.10	-0.03	0.16	0.80	0.82
	RCM	-1	3	9	5	0	1	0.86	0.55	0.64	0.69	0.89	0.93
LE	CMIP5-D	-1	-3	6	1	-4	-3	0.17	0.12	0.22	0.30	0.57	0.70
	RCM	-3	-1	2	-6	-9	-3	0.76	0.77	0.16	-0.01	0.05	0.24
H	CMIP5-D	4	14	17	17	12	7	0.07	-0.33	-0.18	-0.14	-0.01	0.38
	RCM	2	4	7	11	9	4	0.24	0.05	-0.05	0.11	0.55	0.79

284 Table 3. Mean bias and spatial correlation of selected radiation and heat fluxes in Euro-
 285 CORDEX RCMs and their driving GCMs (CMIP5-D) compared to ERA5-Land in Central
 286 Europe from April (IV) to September (IX) in the period 1981–2005.

287 2) TURBULENT HEAT FLUXES

288 The monthly LE of both model ensembles is in excellent agreement with ERA5-Land across
289 the entire growing season (Fig. 2e). Although both ensembles slightly overestimate LE in June
290 and underestimate LE in August, the differences are small, only a few W/m^2 (Table 3). Spatial
291 correlations in RCMs are very low except for spring and generally lower than for radiation
292 fluxes. When the RCM data is checked visually on its native grid, LE is relatively suppressed in
293 RCMs over Central European lowlands while it remains high in ERA5-Land in summer (Fig A2
294 in Appendix A).

295 Compared to ERA5 Land, the monthly H is overestimated by CMPI5-D across the entire
296 growing season and by RCMs mostly in summer (Fig. 2f). In CMIP5-D, the maximum
297 differences reach $+17 \text{ W/m}^2$ (or ca $+80\%$) in June and July (Table 3). In RCMs, the differences
298 are smaller, between $+7$ and $+11 \text{ W/m}^2$ (or ca. $+50\%$). The overestimation of H in CMIP5-D is
299 associated with compensation for the positive biases in global irradiance and NetSW, as shown
300 in Fig. 2a and b. However, the enhancement of H itself is not the only mechanism to compensate
301 for the relatively large bias of NetSW. As already mentioned, there is also stronger energy loss
302 by longwave radiation in CMIP5-D, as is apparent from a positive bias of NetLW (see Fig. 2c).

303 In RCMs, the enhanced global irradiance and NetSW in June and July (up to. $+9 \text{ W/m}^2$)
304 compared to ERA5-Land is fully translated into an increased sum of both turbulent fluxes, H+LE
305 (Table 3). As the energy loss via NetLW is reduced in RCMs in June and July (Fig 2c or Table
306 3), part of the energy is perhaps accumulated in the region via the heat flux into soil or
307 transported horizontally by other mechanisms.

308 4) EVAPORATIVE FRACTION

309 Monthly values of EF in CMIP5-D and ERA5-Land show a gradual increase during the
310 entire growing season that corresponds to the increasing share of LE in the net turbulent heat flux
311 (Fig. 3). In absolute terms, however, the H monthly values are significantly larger in CMIP5-D,
312 thus leading to an EF of approximately 0.7, while in ERA5-Land the EF is higher, around 0.8. In
313 RCMs, the EF values are close to ERA5-Land until June, but then they drop to 0.72 as the role of
314 H grows, while LE declines in RCMs (Fig. 3).

315

316 Fig. 3. Seasonal course of the evaporative fraction in Central Europe from April (IV) to
 317 September (IX) as simulated by Euro-CORDEX RCMs, their driving GCMs (CMIP5-D), and
 318 ERA5-Land (ERA5L) in the period 1981–2005.

319 *b. Climate change projections*

320 The aim of this section is to analyze the future changes of the surface energy budget
 321 components in Euro-CORDEX RCMs and their driving GCMs (CMIP5-D) and put those
 322 changes into a broader perspective of the projections from the larger ensembles of CMIP5 a
 323 CMIP6 models. The RCP8.5 scenario is considered for RCMs and both ensembles of CMIP5
 324 models, while the SSP5-8.5 scenario is taken for CMIP6 GCMs.

325 1) AIR TEMPERATURE

326 All model ensembles expect significant warming toward the end of the 21st century. The
 327 annual mean temperature should increase by +4.4 °C according to CMIP5-D or by slightly less
 328 (+3.8 °C) according to RCMs. Warming is strongest in the second half of the growing season
 329 (July to September) and varies from +4.0 to 4.5 °C in RCMs or from +5.3 to 5.7°C in CMIP5-D
 330 (Fig. 4 top). For most of the year (mainly outside the growing season), the differences between
 331 warming levels in RCMs and CMIP5-D are small: only a few tenths of a degree Celsius (Fig 4
 332 top). However, from June to September, the differences between both ensembles are bigger,
 333 from 1 to 1.4 °C. When the larger CMIP5 ensemble is considered, the warming signal is usually
 334 close to CMIP5-D. In CMIP6 models warming is stronger than in any other ensemble, as the new

335 generation of CMIP6 GCMs show greater climate sensitivity than their CMIP5 counterparts
 336 (Meehl et al., 2020; Zelinka et al., 2020) and their scenario forcing, SSP5-8.5, is also not
 337 identical to RCP8.5. However, the main pattern of air temperature changes across the growing
 338 season remains the same.

339
 340 Fig. 4. Projected changes of monthly air temperature (top) and precipitation (bottom) in
 341 Central Europe in the last quarter of the 21st century according to the RCP8.5 or SSP5-8.5
 342 scenarios in Euro-Cordex RCMs, their driving GCMs (CMIP5-D) and other two larger
 343 ensembles of CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. Whiskers indicate standard deviation of the ensemble
 344 mean changes.

345 2) PRECIPITATION

346 There are two main features in the projected precipitation changes in all model ensembles.
 347 (Fig 4 bottom). First, a reduction in precipitation from July to September (CMIP5-D: from -7 to -
 348 20 mm/month or -35 mm in total; RCMs: from -2 to -9 mm/month or -17 mm in total) that in
 349 case of all GCM ensembles is present already in June (e.g., CMIP5-D: -5 mm/month). Second,
 350 there is an increase in precipitation from October to May (CMIP5-D: from +4 to +15 mm/month

351 or +84 mm in total; RCMs: from +1 to +16 mm/month or +97 mm in total). A combination of
352 both effects leads to higher annual precipitation sums of +43 mm (or +5%) in CMIP5-D and +80
353 mm (or +10%) in RCMs. There's good agreement among all models on the higher monthly
354 precipitation from November to April as indicated by ensemble standard deviations smaller than
355 mean changes (Fig. 4 bottom). The reduction of precipitation in the second half of the growing
356 season is less certain. For RCMs, after a significant increase in precipitation in April and May,
357 changes of precipitation from June to September are insignificant. For CMIP5-D and CMIP5
358 models, all monthly changes from May to September are insignificant except for July. For
359 CMIP6, however, the precipitation decrease from June to September is stronger than in any other
360 ensemble and significant.

361 3) GLOBAL IRRADIANCE

362 The projected changes in global irradiance at the end of the 21st century differ a lot between
363 RCMs and other GCM ensembles.

364 In CMIP5-D global irradiance rises during the entire growing season and October
365 (significantly except for April and May), in July by +23 W/m² and August +21 W/m² (+10% in
366 both months) (Fig. 5a). In other months, the changes in global irradiance are small (a few W/m²)
367 and mainly negative (the most in March: -3.2 W/m²). From April to June, the largest
368 enhancement of global irradiance is detected in the southeastern part of Central Europe, while
369 from July to September, it is in the southwest (Fig. 6). In other GCM ensembles the main pattern
370 of the projected changes is close to CMIP5-D. CMIP6 changes of global irradiance in the
371 growing season are bigger than those of CMIP5-D and always significant.

372 In RCMs, we may also note an increase in global irradiance from July to September
373 (maximum +8.0 W/m² or +4% in July); however, changes are three or even four times smaller
374 than those in GCM ensembles, insignificant except for July (Fig. 5a) and associated with the
375 southwestern part of Central Europe (Fig. 6). Moreover, global irradiance is suppressed in
376 practically all other months, mainly in winter (up to -11% in relative terms) and in spring
377 (March: -12.9 W/m², i.e., -10%; April: 11.0 W/m², i.e., -6%). Strong reduction of global
378 irradiance in spring is a distinct feature of RCMs that is not present in any of GCM ensembles.

379

381

382 Fig. 5. Projected changes of monthly global irradiance (a), NetSW (b), NetLW (c), NetRAD
 383 (d), LE (e) and H (f) in Central Europe in the last quarter of the 21st century according to the
 384 RCP8.5 scenario or SSP5-8.5 scenarios in Euro-Cordex RCMs, their driving GCMs (CMIP5-D)
 385 and other two larger ensembles of CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs. Whiskers indicate standard
 386 deviation of the ensemble mean changes.

387

388 Fig. 6. Changes of global irradiance [W/m^2] from April (IV) to September (IX) in 2076–2100
389 compared to 1981–2005 projected by Euro-CORDEX RCMs and CMIP5-D GCMs.

390 4) OTHER RADIATION FLUXES

391 The future changes of NetSW in all model ensembles are practically identical or slightly
392 lower to the changes of global irradiance (down to -2 W/m^2 in CMIP5-D and down to -5 W/m^2 in
393 RCMs or CMIP6; see Fig. 5b). NetLW changes are small in all model ensembles and mostly
394 insignificant (Fig. 5c). In RCMs they tend to be year-round negative, the most in spring (down to
395 -7 W/m^2). In all GCM families NetLW changes are positive by a few W/m^2 from July to
396 September, but not significantly. NetRAD changes closely follow the changes of NetSW,
397 however, with a lower magnitude (Fig. 5d). NetRAD will increase in all GCM ensembles
398 throughout the whole growing season (e.g., in CMIP5-D in absolute numbers up to $+17 \text{ W/m}^2$ in
399 July, in relative numbers up to 13% in August). All changes are significant except for April. In
400 RCMs NetRAD will remain almost unchanged in April and May. Then NetRAD will rise, but
401 positive changes are significant only in the second half of the growing season and they always
402 fall behind projected changes in CMIP5-D or other GCM ensembles (e.g., in July and August on
403 -8 W/m^2 compared to CMIP5-D).

404 The future growth of NetRAD in all models during the entire or part of the growing season
405 will bring additional energy for the Earth's surface compared to 1981–2005. This energy should
406 be subsequently released in other nonradiative energy fluxes, for instance, via turbulent heat
407 fluxes (H and LE).

408 7) LATENT HEAT FLUX

409 In all GCM ensembles LE will increase from October to June (Fig. 5e), with maximal
410 changes in spring months (e.g., CMIP5-D from $+7$ to $+8 \text{ W/m}^2$ or from $+10$ to $+22\%$). All GCM
411 changes from October till May are significant. From July to September, LE will decrease slightly
412 in GCMs (e.g., CMIP5-D -4 W/m^2 or -6% in August), but changes are not significant in any of
413 the GCM ensemble. Changes in LE are closely related to changes in precipitation (Fig. 4b).
414 However, the relatively weak reduction in LE despite the strong decrease in precipitation in July
415 or August suggests that LE evaporation (and thus evapotranspiration) is perhaps sustained at the
416 expense of soil water storage in this period. The long-term balance between monthly

417 precipitation and evapotranspiration results in negative values for the period May to August and
418 reach cumulatively -85 mm which is about 30 mm more compared to 1981–2005.

419 In the RCMs, the monthly LE will increase only at a rate higher than or like that of the GCM
420 ensembles (Fig. 5e). Even in the second part of the growing season there is almost no grid point
421 in Central Europe where LE would drop less than -2 W/m^2 (not shown) inferring on no
422 pronounced long-term water limitations. The highest growth of LE is again expected to occur in
423 spring with similar magnitude as that in the GCMs. Unlike GCMs the increase of LE is also
424 expected in June ($+7.9 \text{ W/m}^2$) and all positive changes from October till June are significant in
425 RCMs. The changes in LE in the RCMs are again closely related to changes in precipitation.
426 More precipitation (or a weaker reduction from July to September) together with stronger LE
427 flux indicates that there will be a sufficient supply of soil moisture to enable evaporation.
428 Compared to CMIP5-D, the long-term balance between monthly precipitation and
429 evapotranspiration results in negative values only for the period June to August and reach
430 cumulatively -37 mm (i.e. less than half of the water deficit in CMIP5-D) which is about 20 mm
431 more than during 1981–2005.

432 8) SENSIBLE HEAT FLUX

433 According to all GCM ensembles, H will remain unchanged from November to April (Fig.
434 5f). From June to September H will increase significantly, however. In July and August, the
435 CMIP5-D projections suggest H up to $+19 \text{ W/m}^2$ (or +50%) higher than in 1981–2005. While the
436 changes in CMIP5 ensemble are like CMIP5-D, in CMIP6 they are stronger again, on additional
437 $3\text{--}4 \text{ W/m}^2$. Higher values of H will affect only mainland Europe (Fig. 7). During the two-thirds
438 of the Central European growing season, H responds to the elevated global irradiance in all GCM
439 ensembles at most and compensates for the higher income of energy through the absorption of
440 shortwave solar radiation at the surface.

441 In the RCMs, the situation is different. In the spring, especially in April and May, the RCMs
442 expect a reduction in H by -5 W/m^2 (Fig. 5f). This reduction in H is limited to mainland Europe
443 approximately north of 47 degrees of northern latitude (Fig. 7). From July to September, H will
444 increase from $+3$ to $+6 \text{ W/m}^2$, but again, this rate is far behind the changes in the GCM
445 ensembles that are three times stronger in magnitude (Fig. 5f). The amplification of H in the

446 RCMs is the largest in the western part of Central Europe and again limited to the mainland only
 447 (Fig. 7).

448 -34 -30 -26 -22 -18 -14 -10 -6 -2 2 6 10 14 18 22 26 30 34
 449 Fig. 7. Same as Fig. 6 but for sensible heat flux [W/m^2].

450 9) EVAPORATIVE FRACTION

451 Here, we strictly limit our investigation to the growing period, as the EF values may be
 452 distorted in late autumn, winter, and early spring when both H and LE are small and additionally
 453 H is often negative. The EF changes are again different between RCMs on one side and GCM
 454 ensembles on the other side.

455 In CMIP5-D as well as other GCM ensembles, the EF values will decrease except for April
 456 and May when they slightly rise or remain practically unchanged. From July to September, the
 457 EF will drop by -0.10 to -0.12 in CMIP5-D or by -0.12 to -0.17 in CMIP6 (Fig. 8). This is related
 458 to a tiny reduction in LE accompanied by a substantial increase in H and resulting changes of EF
 459 are significant across all GCM ensembles from July to September. In absolute terms from April
 460 to June, the EF values are practically identical to those in the past (i.e., approximately 0.7, see
 461 Fig. 3), while from July to September, they drop to 0.58 in CMIP5-D or 0.53 in CMIP6 reaching
 462 their minimum in August. The most significant declines in EF are in the water-limited
 463 southeastern and western Europe, where we also detect the most prominent changes in LE
 464 (reduction) and H (enhancement). This pattern is then also translated into geographical changes
 465 in EF in Central Europe (Fig. 9).

466

467 Fig. 8. Projected changes of evaporative fraction in Central Europe in the last quarter of the
 468 21st century according to the RCP8.5 scenario or SSP5-8.5 scenarios in Euro-Cordex RCMs,
 469 their driving GCMs (CMIP5-D) and other two larger ensembles of CMIP5 and CMIP6 GCMs.
 470 Whiskers indicate standard deviation of the ensemble mean changes.

471

472 Fig. 9. Same as Fig. 6 but for evaporative fraction.

473 In the RCMs, the EF rises from April to June (April +0.07, May +0.05: changes are
 474 significant) and then drops as in the GCMs but not as strongly (by -0.03 at most; see Fig. 8). The
 475 role of LE on the net turbulent heat exchange is thus stronger and culminates at 0.81 in May.
 476 Then, it declines to 0.7 in July and August to rise again in September to 0.75 (not shown). The
 477 spring increase in EF affects the whole of Central Europe, while its summer reduction is

478 particularly strong in the western part of Central Europe (Fig. 9), where a combined effect of
479 practically unchanged LE (not shown) and elevated H can be seen (Fig. 7).

480 **4. Discussion and Conclusions**

481 We analyzed the surface energy budget of four ensembles of climate models and their future
482 changes in the RCP8.5 or SSP5-8.5 scenario with emphasis on Euro-CORDEX RCMs and their
483 driving CMIP5 GCMs. When RCMs and CMIP5-D are tested in Central Europe against the
484 gridded observational datasets represented by ERA5-Land, E-OBS and SARA2, a surprisingly
485 excellent agreement in the simulated LE in terms of mean bias was found in all months of the
486 growing season in the period of 1981-2005. This suggests that evapotranspiration, a key
487 component of the water cycle, and energy or mass exchange between the land surface and
488 atmosphere, is well, or at least consistently, captured in terms of the size in the recent generation
489 of climate models in Central Europe, even though the spatial distribution of LE doesn't show
490 good agreement with ERA5-Land.

491 The evaluation also reveals the existence of important biases in other fluxes, especially in
492 CMIP5-D. There is a significant overestimation of global irradiance in CMIP5-D that further
493 propagates into other energy fluxes: NetSW, NetLW and H (Fig. 2). As noted by Wild (2020),
494 excessive global irradiance is related to a lack of absorption in the cloud-free atmosphere in the
495 GCMs and persists even in the latest generation of CMIP6 GCMs. It is then translated into
496 increased NetLW and H, leading to their biases when compared to ERA5-Land.

497 Overall, very good agreement between the RCMs and ERA5-Land was found. In some cases,
498 the spatial distribution of energy fluxes and their seasonal courses seem to be even more realistic
499 in the RCMs than in ERA5-Land. First, the spatial distribution of global irradiance is rather
500 smoothed in ERA5-Land (or E-OBS) while in RCMs or CM SAF satellite observation it is more
501 detailed and captures, for instance, a summer reduction of global irradiance over the mountains
502 (Fig A1 in Appendix A). Second, the stronger role of H in RCMs detected in Central Europe
503 (Fig. 5f) and its lowlands in summer (Fig. A2 in Appendix A) corresponds well to the behavior
504 of typical lowland biomes, e.g., crop fields, as confirmed by FLUXNET measurements (Fig. A3
505 in Appendix A). An intensification of H in RCMs is also accompanied by a reduction in LE in
506 the summer months (Fig A2 in Appendix A). ERA5-Land, however, keeps H constant
507 throughout almost the entire growing season (Fig. 2f). Similar behavior is typical for grassland,

508 as indicated by FLUXNET measurements (Fig. A3 in Appendix A). However, this is not a
509 dominant biome of Central Europe. According to the CORINE2020 it represents only 10% of the
510 land surface of Central Europe. The practically constant seasonal course of H in the growing
511 season in ERA5-Land could be explained because of spatial averaging over the study area, where
512 a mixture of forests (32%), crop fields (44%) or pastures (10%) is present. As illustrated by the
513 measurements at FLUXNET sites, these major Central European biomes show very diverse
514 seasonal courses of H and also EF (Fig. A3 in Appendix A). However, even at finer spatial scales
515 in ERA5-Land, for instance, over the large agricultural lowlands of Slovakia, Hungary or Central
516 Bohemia, there is no sign of temporal variability of H that is typical for FLUXNET cropland
517 sites. With respect to the high resolution of ERA5-Land (0.1°) and its maternal ERA5 reanalysis
518 (0.25°) it is surprising. Both examples point on the added value of RCMs as a tool for
519 downscaling global climate models and simulating climate on a regional or local scale.

520 Future changes in all investigated surface energy budget components are mainly affected and
521 driven by changes in global irradiance and the net balance of shortwave radiation. This is where
522 we see an important difference between GCM and RCM simulations, as noted by Bartók et al.
523 (2017) and more closely investigated by Boé et al. (2020) or Taranu et al. (2022).

524 In all GCM ensembles, we see an increase in global irradiance for most of the year that is
525 translated into a year-round enhancement of NetSW. It is then balanced mostly by higher
526 turbulent heat fluxes. In the first two months of the growing season in Central Europe, we see the
527 abundance of water from precipitation in winter and spring that is translated into a higher LE
528 flux and, despite higher temperatures, a constant H. From June to September, the rainfall drops,
529 followed by an immediate increase in H and a subsequent small reduction in LE.
530 Evapotranspiration is likely limited by the soil water supply. The second part of the growing
531 season is warm, sunny, and dry. All GCM projections thus indicate higher likelihood of
532 conditions that may cause drought stress to vegetation due to lack of water and overall decrease
533 in biomass productivity, despite higher CO_2 levels.

534 The situation is less straightforward in the RCMs, where changes in global irradiance and
535 NetSW are balanced differently. There is a reduction in NetLW throughout the year. With
536 respect to rising air temperatures and elevated concentrations of greenhouse gases in the
537 atmosphere, the reduction in NetLW can be explained by the strengthening of downwelling

538 longwave radiation. This is likely due to greater cloudiness, as also indicated by the reduction in
539 global irradiance. The LE flux is enhanced throughout the year, most strongly in spring and early
540 summer, which is again related to high precipitation and warmer climate in winter and spring.
541 Evapotranspiration does not seem to be limited by the soil water supply, as also indicated by the
542 reduced H and simple water balance consideration leading relatively small summer deficits.
543 From July to September, the temperature rises, the rainfall drops, the sky becomes brighter, and
544 the Earth's surface gains more energy, but it is still far less than that in the CMIP5-D.
545 Evapotranspiration is still slightly higher than at present, and compared to H, LE dominates in
546 compensating the small energy gains due to the higher NetSW. The second part of the growing
547 season is warm and sunny but certainly not dry. All this happens under high concentrations of
548 CO₂. The RCM scenarios thus indicate conditions that are favorable for a substantial increase in
549 plant productivity due to the abundance of water or the overall prolonging of the growing season.

550 Although the detected differences between CMIP5-D and RCM projections in Central
551 Europe seem to be insignificant, their combination can have fundamental effects on the
552 estimation of the very nature of the impact of climate change on some sectors. The predictions of
553 the impact models can lead to remarkably different results, which cannot be explained simply by
554 reference to the different resolution or uncertainty in the CMIP5-D and RCM ensembles.

555 Furthermore, when the wider ensemble consisted of 17 CMIP6 GCMs and their projections
556 following the Shared Socioeconomics Pathway (SSP) scenario SSP5-85 is considered,
557 differences between the CMIP5-D or CMIP5 and RCM projections become even more
558 pronounced. Although the SSP5-85 and RCP8.5 scenarios are not identical and the new
559 generation CMIP6 models show greater climate sensitivity than their CMIP5 counterparts
560 (Meehl et al. 2020; Zelinka et al. 2020), the overall pattern of the future changes of air
561 temperature, precipitation, and surface energy budget components in the CMIP6 ensemble is
562 closer to both CMIP5 ensembles and further away from RCMs (Fig. 5). Warming is generally
563 stronger in CMIP6 and associated with a more significant reduction of precipitation in the
564 growing season. The global irradiance increase is also stronger, especially from April to June.
565 LE and H changes in CMIP6 follow a similar pattern as in CMIP5 ensembles, but again the
566 magnitude of change is bigger. Their combined effect leads to larger reduction of EF in the

567 growing season. There is no sign of heading toward the wetter growing season in Central
568 Europe.

569 It is also worth noting that the observed data in Central Europe show the following:

570 a) increase in global irradiance in the first half of the growing season (Trnka et al. 2015)

571 b) long-term stagnation of annual precipitation (Brázdil et al. 2022)

572 c) prolongation of drought episodes (Trnka et al. 2016)

573 d) reduction of water supply in the soil (Trnka et al. 2015; Trnka et al. 2022; Scherrer et al.
574 2022)

575 e) decrease in river discharge (Fischer et al. 2023; Torbenson et al. 2023)

576 f) reduction of underground water supply (Hellwig and Stahl 2018).

577 All of the abovementioned phenomena are compatible with the GCM projections of the
578 Central European climate in the 21st century. On the other hand, climate conditions projected by
579 RCMs in Central Europe have a significantly weaker fingerprint in observations thus far,
580 although the signal of human-induced global climate change has already been present in
581 observations for many decades. Euro-CORDEX RCM simulations obtained by downscaling
582 CMIP5-D result in changes in global irradiance, turbulent heat fluxes or precipitation that lead to
583 conditions favorable for landscape water accumulation and plant growth in the growing season in
584 Central Europe. This is, however, in contradiction with the story told by CMIP5-D and trends
585 derived from observations. Although the added value of RCMs and their suitability for use in
586 impact studies is evident, in the case of the conflicting nature of RCM and GCM projections, the
587 emphasis on using RCM-based projections in further modeling and decision-making chains
588 might lead to a serious risk of maladaptation and inefficiencies in mitigating climate change.

589 Our results thus confirm the ongoing need for more detailed investigation and better
590 understanding of causes that lead to differences among climate projections from different model
591 ensembles, as has already been initiated by the climate modeling community (Fernández et al.
592 2019; Schwingshackl et al. 2019; Boé et al. 2020; Taranu et al. 2022). It is worth noting that in
593 Euro-CORDEX experiments downscaling CMIP5 models in higher spatial resolution of 0.11°,
594 there are RCMs with evolving aerosols and thus different evolution of air temperature or global

595 irradiance (Schumacher et al. in press). Our results for Euro-CORDEX 0.44° RCMs do not
596 comprise the full available CORDEX RCM ensemble. For future use of RCMs, we suggest
597 introducing preliminary test of RCMs by using their data in impact models to critically examine
598 a cumulative effect of potential biases that may be hidden in RCMs. Comparing these outputs
599 with the observations may serve as an indirect validation of RCMs prior to their recommendation
600 as a tool for impact studies. In light of the arrival of a new generation of Euro-CORDEX
601 projections based on the downscaling of CMIP6 GCMs, this is a timely note that may help to
602 support and confirm the choice of the most suitable RCMs for impact modeling in all parts of
603 Europe.

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609 investigators of FLUXNET sites for their kind permission to use their data for illustration
610 purposes in our work.

611 *Data availability statement.*

612 GCM and RCM data are available via the ESGF data nodes (see, e.g.,
613 <https://esgf.llnl.gov/nodes.html>). ERA5-Land and E-OBS data are available via Climate Data
614 Store of Copernicus Climate Change Services (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu#!/home>).
615 SARAH-2 data were obtained via the Web User Interface at the CM SAF
616 (https://wui.cmsaf.eu/safira/action/viewHome?menuName=HOME_CMSAF_WUI). FLUXNET
617 station data were collected by Alexander Graf from managers of individual FLUXNET sites.

618

619

APPENDIX A

620

FLUXNET stations and evaluation of RCMs and CMIP5-D GCMs

621 We used measurements of surface energy balance components from selected stations of the
622 FLUXNET network in Central Europe to illustrate surface turbulent heat fluxes behavior in
623 different biomes typical for Central Europe and to compare with climate model data. The data

624 from FLUXNET sites cover the period 2001–2018; however, availability may differ among
 625 stations (Table A1).

Map ID	Biome	Site	Altitude	Longitude	Latitude	Data Coverage	Reference
A	crop	Oensingen	452	7.734	47.286	2004-2018	Emmel et al. (2018)
B	grass	Chamau	400	8.410	47.210	2006-2018	Feigenwinter et al. (2023)
C	forest	Hainich	440	10.453	51.079	2001-2018	Knohl et al. (2003)
D	crop	Gebesee	162	10.914	51.100	2001-2018	
E	crop	Klingenberg	478	13.522	50.893	2005-2018	Prescher et al. (2010)
F	grass	Grillenburg	385	13.513	50.950	2003-2018	Prescher et al. (2010)
G	forest	Tharandt	380	13.565	50.963	2001-2018	Prescher et al. (2010)
H	forest	Bílý Kříž	875	18.537	49.502	2004-2018	

626 Table A1. Availability of radiation and heat flux data from the selected FLUXNET stations
 627 representing various biomes in Central Europe.

628

629 Fig. A1. Monthly mean global irradiance [W/m^2] in July derived from Euro-CORDEX
 630 RCMs, ERA5-Land, E-OBS and CM SAF SARA-2 data (clockwise from the top left corner) in
 631 the period 1981–2005.

632

633

634 Fig. A2. Monthly mean latent (top) and sensible (bottom) heat flux [W/m^2] in July derived
 635 from Euro-CORDEX RCM (left) and ERA5-Land (right) in the period 1981–2005.

636

637

638 Fig. A3. Seasonal course of sensible heat flux [W/m^2] (top row) and evaporative fraction
 639 (bottom row) from April (IV) to September (IX) at selected Central European FLUXNET sites
 640 representing various biomes: grassland (left column), cropland (center column) and forest
 641 (right column).

642

643

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